

Real Time Virtual Apparel Simulator

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Abstract — In this project, we will work on the design and implementation of augmented reality ‘virtual dressing room’ for real-time simulation of 3D clothes. The system is developed using a single Microsoft Kinect Sensor as the depth sensor, to obtain user body parameter measurements, including 3D measurements and develop a unique model for each user. This system will physically simulate the selected virtual clothes on the user’s body in real time and the user can see the virtual clothes fitting on the mirror image from various angles as the user moves.

Keywords—Kinect Sensor, Visual Studio, C#, Windows Presentation Foundation, Kinect Studio, CLO.

I. Introduction

Trying clothes in clothing stores is usually a time-consuming activity. Moreover, it might not even be possible to try on clothes in the store, such as when ordering clothes online. In fact a study has shown that around 61.2% people use the Internet just to buy clothes. A busy lifestyle led people to buy readymade clothes from retail stores with or without fit-on, expecting a perfect match. The existing online cloth shopping systems are capable of providing only 2D images of the clothes, which does not lead to a perfect match for the individual user. To overcome this problem, we design and implement a virtual apparel simulator for real time simulation of 3D clothes.

Our intention is that by creating a virtual fitting room environment we can improvise approachability of trying clothes on and need not have to waste time we need to have the correct measurement of the user and the dress model with correct rotation, measurement, location. For the system implementation, we used a Kinect V1 sensor equipped with several sensors that can detect the depth using an IR sensor, capture RGB images (video) using a camera sensor, and capture audio using an inbuilt microphone array, Kinect sensor has an internal processor to process and manipulate data before sending to the software development kit (SDK), reducing the workload on the PC side, developed system consists of two applications, Kinect studio application captures user body measurements, and the UNITY 3D application overlays the cloth model on the user in front of the device, necessary body parameters for clothing, such as height, shoulder length, arm length, inseam, and neck-to-hip length, are calculated incorporating the Kinect skeleton joints, complex body parameters such as perimeters at the chest, waist, hip, thigh, and knee are calculated using information obtained from the depth sensor of the

Kinect, applicability of a single depth sensor to measure human body parameters was also investigated.

II. Literature Review

[1] In the “Applicability of a single depth sensor in real-time 3D clothes simulation: Augmented reality virtual dressing room using Kinect sensor”, the author has used Microsoft’s V2 depth sensor to gather the necessary user body parameters of the person standing in front of the Kinect sensor device. Then the overlapping application is launched with all measure parameters to filter the 3D cloth models based on gender. Finally the application appends the physics animation to the dress according to the physical movements made by the user providing a realistic fitting experience.

[2] In the “Virtual shopping using Kinect”, the author has used a Kinect sensor to capture the physical measurement of consumers and create a 3-D model for them the present three scenarios for virtual try-on of clothes, i.e., i) Avatar Only (AO): virtual clothes on an avatar, ii) Dress Only (DO): virtual clothes on a user’s image, and iii) Hybrid Version (HV): virtual clothes on an avatar blended with a user’s face image. Then a novel algorithm is used to properly align a 3D customized avatar with the user’s image in real-time. The user sees a lookalike avatar on the screen wearing virtual clothes.

[3] In the “A mixed reality virtual clothes try-on system”, the author has used a Kinect camera for the pose detection, body measurement, user segmentation and face skin color detection. The avatar is then automatically customized according to the extracted sizes and skin color. The user can then select his/her favorite virtual clothes for virtual try on. The selected virtual clothes will be aligned on the user’s image, physically simulated and rendered in real-time.

[4] In the “Virtual Fitting by Single Shot Body Shape Estimation”, the author has created a database of 2D image of each clothing for on different body shapes and use 3D body shape models from single-shot depth images to identify the body shape and overlay the clothing over their body image taken using depth image.

[5] In the “A Body & Garment Creation Method for Internet Based Virtual Fitting Room”, the author has created a 3D model in an online platform, where the user can see the fitting of the selected apparel in 3D form. The dimensions of the 3D will be based on the average human for each gender. The clothes which were first

designed in 2D plane will be placed and formed around the 3D humanoid model and fit as per generalized dimensions.

[6] In the “Real Time Virtual Mirror Using Kinect”, the author has used the Kinect sensor to create a skeleton structure of the user. They have used 2D images of the clothing which will be fitted on the skeleton using the shoulders and hips as reference points.

[7] In the “Real Time Virtual Clothes Try On System”, the authors have used a Motion and Skeleton Capture Sensor to compute the user's measurements. They have then compared the computed body size with the measurements in the body size standards to make an estimate of the user's body size. They developed a particular background which helped them to accurately compute body measurements. Finally, the clothes can be selected by hand movements from the list option displayed on the screen and the user can then view it virtually displayed on their body.

[8] In the “Human Friendly Interface Design for Virtual Fitting Room Applications on Android Based Mobile Devices”, The authors have developed a real time, platform independent application for virtual fitting rooms. They have used Augmented and Virtual Reality and Face Detection for their project. They have also added a feature where the user can choose different sizes from XS to XL and also different cameras on the device. Apart from this, they also used various techniques like Canny Edge Detection and Motion Detection to achieve their main objective. The algorithm which they designed can track and scale the clothing according to user's position and movement very accurately.

[9] In the “Virtual Dressing Room Application with Virtual Human Using Kinect Sensor”, the authors designed a system which enables users to try virtual clothes and shoes with the help of their hand movements which select clothes from a list on the screen. After this, the selected clothes appear on a humanoid model and the user chooses the size he/she wants and also the skin color to get a more realistic effect. For multiple viewing angles, they also developed an optional mirror selection button. The tools they used are Kinect Sensor and Unity 3D Game Engine.

[10] In the “3D Virtual Dressing Room application”, the authors have used the modules for locations of the joints for positioning, scaling and rotation in order to align the 2D cloth models with the user. Then, they have applied skin color detection to handle the unwanted occlusions of the user and the model. Finally, the model is superimposed on the user in real time. Several approaches are proposed for body part detection, skeletal tracking and posture estimation, and superimposing it onto a virtual environment in the user interface. This project is implemented in a C programming environment for real time, Kinect hacking application. Kinect driver's middleware are used for various fundamental functions and for the tracking process in combination with Microsoft Kinect.

[11] In the “A Real Time Virtual Dressing Room Application Using Kinect ”, the author has detected the skeletal tracking of the user in a video stream. They used conceptual motion capture which proposed a tag based augmented reality dressing room which required sticking virtual tags for motion tracking. They also used Kinect SDK that helped in developing the Application based Kinect sensor.

[12] In the “Virtual Fitting Space for Dress Trials”, the authors have used skeleton detection method to identify the human (user) and human contour detection method to find out the outline of the human or user. Moreover, different positions of the human body are detected using the Haar cascade classification method (Machine learning concept) and warping process is used to resize the outfit according to the size of the human body.

III. Kinect Sensor

The Microsoft V1 Kinect Sensor is used to capture the user's body information, such as measurements and body movements. The Kinect Sensor is a horizontal bar which consists of an IR projector and an IR camera which detects depth. It also has an RGB Camera which senses color and a Microphone for Speech recognition. For our project, We will be using an adapter which will act as a medium to connect the Kinect sensor with our laptop.

IV. Methodology

We had created and formed a proposed architecture which we planned to follow:

Following this we installed all the necessary softwares, which is required to interface Kinect Sensor with our computer such as the Kinect Software Development Kit along with Kinect Studio which contains few example programmes for us to understand the working of the Kinect Sensor.

We first started off with designing all the virtual clothing. We went on using CLO software which is meant for designing virtual easily and efficiently. The CLO software is very User Friendly for beginners to professionals who can design clothing within a matter of a few hours.

Our plan of action was to use one of the example codes and run the code in Visual Studio which will help us edit the code, where we can add our Virtual Clothing. Later on align the virtual clothing.

A. Kinect Studio Program

We looked into various codes for our project such as Skeleton Basics:

As we can see, this program only gives us the skeleton output which is important to align all the virtual clothing. But without the user being able to see themselves, which makes them unable to see and judge if the apparel suits them. In this program the depth is not being scanned which makes it difficult for the clothing to adjust itself with respect to the user's body structure.

Then we looked into another program Kinect Fusion Basics:

As we can see, this program only gives us the user's body structure output which helps to adjust the fitting of all the virtual clothing with respect to the user's body. But without the user being able to see themselves properly without a camera it makes them unable to see and judge if the apparel suits them. In this program the skeleton is not being scanned which makes it difficult for the clothing to align itself as the skeleton structure gives us a reference point where the clothing is attached.

Then lastly we looked into another program Kinect Explorer:

As we can see, this program gives us all the parameters we need for our project. Skeleton Structure which is used as reference points to place and align all the virtual clothing. Depth Structure which is used to adjust the clothing with respect to the user's body structure.

B. Kinect and Clothing Interface

When it came to interfacing the virtual clothing with the respective Kinect program, we faced a few difficulties and later on we came up with our own method for our problem. We tried out 3 different methods for this.

First Visual Studio method. From our research we have found that Kinect Sensor can be connected and run using Visual Studio. We connected our kinect sensor and used Kinect Explorer D2D code from Kinect Software Development Kit. We did a test run where the code was seen to run successfully. We converted our virtual clothes which we designed in CLO software into .fbx or .obj format for Visual Studio as .Zprj of CLO was not acceptable. Once we add our virtual clothing in the program file. The code does not work and shows errors regarding the added files. We tried to find a solution but couldn't make it work.

Second Unity 3D method. Since Visual Studio didn't work as the platform for us to work on we searched for a different method, where Unity3D software was used as the platform to connect kinect sensor and virtual clothing. For this we needed to download a few packages and library, which is to be imported in Unity3D. Even though we followed all the steps exactly how it was meant to be, our kinect sensor was not able to connect to the Unity3D software. While we are still working on this, we are working on the third method.

Third C# and Windows Presentation Foundation method. This method is developed by us. We used Windows Presentation Foundation and C# for this method. We used SkeletonBasics WPF code from Kinect Software Development Kit. This code was written in C# which serves the backend functionality and WPF serves the frontend Graphic User Interface. The base idea was to create 3D objects (Virtual Clothes) in C# and merge its code with the original SkeletonBasic code. The merge can happen by writing the object in the form of functions and calling all the object functions in the main class. When it came to actually executing our theoretical idea, we realized objects are created in WPF and then added and aligned in the main code using C#. We are still working on this method. We have created experimental objects and added the Main Window. Now we will be focusing on C# where the object will be used as testing this method. Once successfully added the object in the code, we can see the object and user in one frame. We will align the object with respect to the Skeleton structure displayed in the output, and also see to it that the object follows the skeleton as the subject moves around.

V. Conclusion

The skeleton of the customer is detected by the Kinect Device using the IR-camera and RGB-camera based on the skeleton joints of the body. After determining the joints, we will frame the human structure. The dresses are then viewed on the human structure in a 3-dimensional manner to give a realistic look of the virtual apparel on the customer. The virtual clothes move according to the motion of the customer. The main purpose of our project is to enable customers to try on different clothes virtually in front of a screen which will help them choose the best-matched outfit with a new stimulating experience. After working with 3 different methods to interface virtual clothing with kinect sensor, we found our C# and WPF method to give us more satisfactory results as compared to previous 2 methods. This method is also much easier to work with as the entire code is written in a single script as compared to its C++ counterpart which had multiple scripts for each function.

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